

Correspondence fragments PAM 44.102 (vis-à-vis PAM 43.681, 44.081)

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In the DJD edition (DJD 33) of Plates with Unidentified Fragments photographed on PAM 43.660 through 43.701, two photographs were not included, namely PAM 43.687 since it includes (mainly) fragments of 4Q418a, and PAM 43.681, which has been replaced by PAM 44.102 which contains many of the same fragments as PAM 43.681.

However, PAM 43.681 and PAM 44.102 only partially overlap. The bottom two-thirds of the both photographs largely overlap. Hence, the top rows of PAM 43.681 are not on PAM 44.102, whereas the top rows of PAM 44.102 consist almost entirely of fragments from the bottom of PAM 44.081.

The lists below give a basic overview of the photographic provenance of the fragments of PAM 44.102, their present Museum Plate and identification.

DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, eds., *Qumran Cave 4. XXIII: Unidentified Fragments.*

Discoveries in the Judean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)

IAA Israel Antiquities Authority

PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum

PAM 44.081: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285092>

PAM 44.102: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284999>

Previous photograph	PAM 44.102	Later PAM photos	IAA Plate	Assignment manuscript
44.081	1		196	
44.016	2		467, 2	4Q367 1a (DJD 13)
44.081	3		?	
44.081	4		196	
44.081	5		?	
44.081	6	44.197	123, 2*	4Q424 3* (DJD 36)
44.081	7		196	
44.081	8		196	
44.081	9		?	
44.081	10		196	
44.081	11		196	

44.081	12		196	
44.081	13		196	
44.081	14		196	
44.081	15		196	Exod 12:16-17 doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5123240
44.081	16		196	4Q447 (DJD 29)
44.081	17		?	
44.081	18		?	
44.081	19		196	
44.081	20		196	
44.081	21		196	
44.081	22		196	4Q464b 2 (DJD 19)
44.081	23		196	
	24		?	
44.081	25		196	
43.681	26		196	
43.681	27		?	
43.681	28		196	
43.681	29		196	
44.081	30		196	
43.681	31		196	4Q364 4a (DJD 13)
44.081	32		196	
43.681	33		196	
43.681	34		196	
43.681	35		196	4Q385a A / 4Q383 5 (DJD 30)
43.681	36		196	
43.681	37		196	
43.681	38		196	
43.681	39		196	
43.681	40		196	
43.681	41		196	
43.681	42		196	
43.681	43		196	
43.681	44		196	
44.081	45		196	
44.081	46		196	
43.681	47		196	

43.681	48		196	
43.681	49		196	
43.681	50		196	
43.681	51		196	
43.681	52	44.195	267, 24	
43.681	53	44.195	267, 21	
43.681	54	44.195	267, 19	
43.681	55		196	
43.681	56		196	
43.681	57		196	
43.681	58		196	
43.681	59		196	
43.681	60		196	
43.681	61		196	
43.681	62		196	
43.681	63		196	
43.681	64		196	
43.681	65		196	
43.681	66		196	4Q273a (<i>Meghillot</i> 15)
43.681	67		196	
43.681	68		196	
43.681	69		196	
43.681	70		196	
43.681	71	44.198		4Q103a (<i>Revue de Qumran</i> 20/77)
43.681	72		196	
43.681	73		196	
43.681	74	44.198	?	
43.681	75		196	
43.681	76		?	
43.681	77		?	
43.681	78		196	
43.681	79		196	
43.681	80		196	
43.681	81 (actually 44.101)		196	4Q440b (DJD 36)

bottom part of PAM 44.081

bottom PAM 43.681 (left) and bottom PAM 44.102 (right)